

Publishable Summary for 20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air

Overview

Given that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials and other products used indoors into the air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate, traceable measurements of the emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection. For the traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials, this project has developed candidate emission reference materials (ERM) with defined and almost stable emission profiles, and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the quality control requirements of the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516. The project results will support the efforts to minimise the use of building products, that emit dangerous substances, thereby ensuring improved indoor air quality.

Need

EU regulation No 305/2011/EU (Construction Products Regulation, CPR) codifies that emissions from building products must be controlled to meet the formulated basic requirements (BR) for construction works. This takes place either on the manufacturer side or in test laboratories accredited under ISO/IEC 17025. EN 16516 prescribes a test procedure for the determination of VOC emissions from construction materials in environmental test chambers whose results are used for the Declaration of Performance (DoP) demanded by the CPR demonstrating conformity with the BR. Furthermore, the test chambers results will be used for the mandatory health-related evaluation of these products, once a harmonised evaluation concept defining emission classes is available in Europe. Comparability between measurement results is fundamentally important, as such, EN 16516 demands verification of the performance of the whole method by comparing against external references and the participation in round robin tests (RRT). For this purpose, both ERM and gCRM are urgently needed.

Findings from studies related to the development of reference materials for emission test chamber measurements often did not consider long-term stability over a time period > 100 hours, in contrast to the standard testing time of 28 days. In previous RRT performed with commercial materials, the relative standard deviations of reproducibility between labs varied from 46 % to 300 %. In addition, a common factor with such approaches is a decreasing emission profile, thus making it difficult to predict the emission rate, which is essential for an external reference. This project met these issues by developing candidate ERMs with reproducible and homogenous emission properties. They are more stable than the first approach of an artificial one on lacquer basis developed in the former EMRP project ENV01 MACPoll and supplemented with a suitable numerical model describing the mass transport inside the material which enables the prediction of the VOC release and allow accurate performance verification of test chambers. In view of the great variety of dangerous substances occurring in indoor air, gCRM containing the compounds of the EN 16516 check standard have been developed.

Objectives

The overall goal of this project was to provide reference materials to improve the traceable measurement and characterisation of emissions of VOCs from materials for interior use according to EN 16516 and to provide CEN/TC 351/WG 2 and other standardisation committees related to materials emissions testing with validation data for future revision of their standards. The specific objectives were:

1. To develop an emission reference material (ERM) that contains and releases relevant compounds typically emitted by construction products within the range of the EU-LCI list with a constant emission profile that decreases by less than 10 % over at least 14 days, in order to improve the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of the emission test chamber method as described in EN 16516.
2. To develop gaseous certified reference materials (gCRM) of indoor air pollutants for compounds selected from key groups that are relevant for the health-related evaluation of building products as stated in the EU-LCI-list, such as aldehydes, unsaturated aldehydes, cyclic dimethylsiloxanes and glycol compounds.
3. To validate the newly developed ERM and gCRM by investigating the short- and long-term stability, reproducibility, and uncertainty in an inter-laboratory comparison, thereby demonstrating the benefits of the reference materials for the test procedure described in EN 16516.
4. To develop a suitable numerical model for simulating the transport processes inside the ERM and the compound release into test chamber air enabling the prediction of the emissions for each of the selected target VOC. The model should support the customised generation of the ERM. All relevant process parameters affecting the release of the compounds from the material will be determined.
5. To contribute to the standards development work of the technical committees CEN/TC351 WG2 and ISO/TC146 SC6 to ensure that the outputs of the project are aligned with their needs, communicated promptly to those developing the standards and to those who will use them (e.g., test chamber operators and gas standards manufacturers), and in a form that can be incorporated into the standards at the earliest opportunity.

Progress beyond the state of the art

Within the preceding EMRP project ENV01 MACPoll an important approach towards a candidate ERM was made with a lacquer material that was added with a selection of VOCs. However, production reproducibility was only shown within the batch of the lacquer material and the emission profile for this decreased rapidly after its application. Furthermore, colligative effects of the added VOCs in terms of miscibility, volatilisation or chemical reactions during curing were reported.

This project has developed materials with retarded compound release leading to a temporarily constant emission profile or at least a significantly decelerated one. It finally worked best for 2 VOCs, *n*-hexadecane and D-limonene. Porous materials, such as zeolites, metal organic frameworks (MOF) and activated charcoal were impregnated with the target compounds under overpressure conditions. In another approach VOCs were encapsulated (core-shell principle). In both cases stable emission profiles with a decrease between 1–10 % within at least 14 days could be achieved, although an aging time of ~10 days is required to reach this stable phase for the capsule material. Although similar results were also obtained with other VOCs in zeolites, this was only possible with exposure to dry test chamber air due to their hygroscopicity. However, contrary to the lacquer approach, the new ERMs have a storage-stability of at least 12 months which enables the production of larger batches to compensate the still mediocre reproducibility. Moreover, it is possible to combine them without the issue of colligative effects.

Based on data obtained by material characterisation regarding all parameters that have an impact on the compound release, a numerical model was developed enabling the calculation of the emission profile for the VOCs introduced. As the reference material will be used in emission test chambers, temperature, pressure, and air velocity above the surface were investigated. Based on that, in a first step, a simplified mathematical model based on the mass balances of the test chamber and the ERM has been implemented. With this, the controlling phenomena inside the test chamber were identified and used for a Finite Element Model (FEM) to characterise the material performance.

The availability of Primary Reference Materials in gaseous form (gPRM) and gCRM have been improved. Test gases available today that contain compounds as stated in the EU-LCI list are mostly not certified and traceability to SI units is rarely demonstrated. In this project, high quality gPRMs and gCRMs were developed containing the components of the so-called check standard defined in EN 16516. When they are generated dynamically, uncertainties below 5 % can be reached. For gPRM prepared in a gas cylinder it came up that phenol was not stable and the uncertainties of most of the other compounds were greater than the targeted 5 %.

Within an inter-laboratory comparison with 8 participants from the stakeholder community the usability of the ERMs, gPRMs and gCRMs as reference materials for the verification of the performance of the test method EN 16516 and to obtain data on the total measurement uncertainty involving all parts of the method were provided for the first time.

Results

Development of an ERM with consistent emissions for QA/QC of the EN 16516 emission test chamber method (Objective 1)

Reservoir materials serving as temporally constant emission sources in a size range of 15 and 50 μm were synthesised with *n*-hexane, *n*-heptane, toluene, D-limonene, and alpha-pinene in the core. The capsules were obtained through polyaddition/polycondensation interface reaction in direct (oil-in-water) emulsion and provided in the form of aqueous suspensions. Depending on the VOC and its properties as to density, miscibility with water and isocyanate(s), as well as interfacial VOC/water tension, the optimisation of the synthesis parameters had to be done for each VOC. Finally, D-limonene and toluene were used as model substances for the investigations on effect of crosslinker(s), surfactant type and monomers ratio. The obtained capsules were characterized in terms of colloidal stability, particle size, morphology, encapsulation yield, chemical composition, and capsules' shell porosity. Emission tests according to EN 16516 revealed that capsule types containing D-limonene and with the shell materials GTIL and HDTTL have provided stable emission profiles within 5–10 % decrease over 14 days.

In a parallel approach, reservoirs made from porous materials (zeolites, a MOF, nanoporous carbons) impregnated with the VOCs *n*-hexane, *n*-heptane, *n*-hexadecane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, butyl acetate, butyl glycol, cyclohexanone, 2-ethoxyethanol, methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) in a high-pressure process were produced. It was found for measurements in dry test chamber air, that the hygroscopic materials FD-107 and 13X APG fulfil the stability requirement for the emission rate of less than 10 % change of the emission rate over 14 days (ΔER), when impregnated with *n*-hexane, *n*-heptane and toluene. Non-hygroscopic materials, such as zeolites with a high Si/Al ratio, activated carbons, or metal organic framework (MOF) showed similar results under dry and humid testing conditions. Most material/VOC combinations have shown mediocre results in humid air. However, two combinations (zeolite BEA/*n*-hexadecane and activated carbon C 40/4/*n*-hexadecane) showed very good (ΔER of 1–10 %) to good (ΔER of 2–34 %) results.

Measurements of both ERM types have indicated eligibility for stabilisation of the emission profile in terms of the goals of Objective1. A detailed report on the ERM development as well as a good practice guide have been published (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12545171>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12544117>).

Development of gaseous certified reference materials of indoor air pollutants relevant for the health-related evaluation of building materials as stated in the EU-LCI list (Objective 2)

Gaseous primary and certified reference materials (gPRM and gCRM) have been prepared for the compounds demanded by EN 16516 in the so-called check standard, with the exception of *n*-hexadecane that cannot be used in gas cylinders due to its low volatility. Instead of 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene as prescribed by the test standard, the consortium in consultation with the stakeholder advisory board had selected 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene. The former was only available in poor purity, which cannot be used in a reference material.

Three types of cylinders with inert inner surfaces for the preparation of the gPRM and two types of adsorbents for the gCRM (Tenax[®] TA and multi-bed) were tested. Dynamic methods were set up to generate a gas mixture of the selected components in air according to ISO 6145-4. Sorbent tubes were sampled to obtain the gCRMs, and the short-term stability test of 28 days could be successfully finished.

Preparation of static gas mixtures with phenol was not possible. During or after preparation phenol decomposed, precipitated as a solid and/or absorbed to the cylinder wall. Fortunately, it was possible to prepare dynamic gas mixtures with phenol. Both the static and dynamic gPRMs could be sampled onto sorbent

tubes to obtain gCRMs to serve as transfer standards. They can be used for calibration and validation purposes.

In addition to that, a gPRM for formaldehyde was under development. For this, paraformaldehyde or 1,3,5-trioxane was used and thermally converted to formaldehyde before mixture preparation. During the project, the optimal temperature for the conversion was determined, 99.8 % of the 1,3,5-trioxane was converted to formaldehyde after 3 hours at 240 °C. In the last months of the project, several gas mixtures in high pressure cylinders of approximately 1 ppm formaldehyde in nitrogen were prepared. In the future, the mixture preparation still needs to be validated, by determining the stability of the gas mixtures.

With the development of the gPRMs and gCRMs the aims of Objective 2 were achieved. A detailed report on the development has been published (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8189413>).

Validation of the newly developed ERM, gPRM and gCRM (Objective 3)

a) Internal validation

The internal validation of the ERM involved investigations of the repeatability, reproducibility as well as short and long-term stability. For this purpose, sets of ERMs including the two activated carbons C 40/4 impregnated with *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, C 45/4 impregnated with toluene, and μ -capsules filled with D-limonene were produced. These sets were distributed between two consortium partners for storing for 14 days, 1, 3, 6, and 12 months at 25 °C (standard storage conditions), 35 °C, 5–10 °C, and -18 °C and subsequent measurement in an emission test chamber. Samples were taken exactly after 24 h (1 day), 72 h (3 days), 168 h (7 days), 240 h (10 days), 336 h (14 days), 504 h (21 days) and 672 h (28 days) for each chamber test.

Repeatability was investigated by measuring six replicates of the same ERM batches revealing a very good homogeneity for the toluene impregnated C 45/4 and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample, mediocre homogeneity for the *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 samples. No trend was found for any of the storage conditions of the stability study. Since the storage did not seem to have any influence, the same results were used to calculate the in-batch reproducibility. This revealed that the ERMs are stable, so that large batches of ERM can be produced, characterised, and used for at least 12 months. This is an advantage over the lacquer approach from ENV01 MACPoll, for example, which is not stable. The measurements showed that colligative effects, which were also reported from the previous project, were not present here.

For the static gPRMs prepared in high pressure cylinders by gravimetry all three cylinder treatments showed initial loss of several VOCs. Treatment 2 showed long-term instability for several components, treatment 1 only for *o*-xylene and treatment 3 for none. The initial loss could be caused during preparation of the gas mixture or due to absorption to the cylinder wall. Thereafter, the gas mixtures were stable for all VOCs when using cylinder type 3. The uncertainty budget for the gPRM was determined, and relative expanded uncertainties of 5 % were obtained for gPRMs prepared dynamically, containing phenol. Static gPRMs, in cylinders, have relative expanded uncertainties between 8–16 %. Cylinder treatment 3 shows the best results for the stability, with no long-term instability for the VOCs.

Both the static and dynamic gPRMs can be sampled into sorbent tubes to obtain gCRMs. The VOCs sampled into sorbent tubes are stable for a period of 28 days. This is the first time that primary gaseous references are available for the check standard. The work also paves the way for the development of gPRMs for other VOCs relevant for indoor air monitoring.

b) External validation

To demonstrate the proof of concept, an inter-laboratory comparison (ILC) was organised using the gCRM and ERM. The ILC involved 2 parts: 1) Analysis of gCRMs; 2) Emission test chamber method with ERMs. For each part, 8 laboratories, i.a. belonging to the stakeholder group, participated.

With the use of the gCRM, it was shown that this reference material can be used for this application and as a check material according to EN 16516, section 8.2.2.3. These reference materials are traceable to the international standards and therefore primary standards as required by the EN 16516 (section 8.4.2).

The ERMs were validated in ILC part 2. At least one material (the toluene impregnated C 40/4 powder) performed very well. It has a reasonable emission rate and a low variability of only 18 %. This proves, that the laboratories' emission testing capabilities are generally good at least under less challenging conditions (i.e., reasonable chamber air concentration and toluene is usually easily detectable). Two other materials (*n*-hexane impregnated BEA powder and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 powder) showed low emission rates and

high variabilities. The μ -capsules showed very unsatisfying results contrary to the internal validation, i.e., very low emission and thus only a few valid measurement results were obtained.

Another conclusion that could be drawn was that the participants' uncertainty evaluation did not include all significant sources of uncertainty and that generally more effort should be put in this issue.

With the validation of the ERM, gPRM and gCRM and the performance of the ILC the aims of Objective 3 were achieved. A detailed summary report on the validation work as well as on the preparation and measurement uncertainty of the reference products have been published (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12545048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13163378>).

Development of a suitable numerical model to predict the compound release out of the ERM (Objective 4)

Based on the general mass balance of the system emission reference material (ERM) – emission test chamber (EC) and the balance of the VOCs within the ERM, a simplified model was developed. The model was fed with data from the emission test chamber characterisation (distribution of the temperature and relative humidity, air velocity caused by the ventilator) and the first ERM prototypes from Objective 1. The Biot number was used as indicator of the controlling phenomenon within the ERM–EC system. With the model it was possible to identify the conditions at which the internal transport was the controlling step. In the second step, by finite element modelling (FEM), the emission of the VOC from the top surface of the ERM into the air/gas layer with the prescribed thickness above the ERM could be described.

The work revealed that the influence quantities with the most important contributions to the uncertainty of the FEM prediction for a system of a porous material and a VOC are the concentration of the sample, the effective diffusion coefficient of the material and the number of air exchanges within the chamber. The model is able to predict the concentration after 7 days. To be able to predict the concentration, an effective diffusion coefficient must be available for the specific material–VOC combination. The way to calculate it was shown. Further outcomes of the modelling work have been the recommendations to use smaller chambers (< 200 L) with higher reproducible velocities to maintain a high Biot number (> 1000). This is intended to make the system ERM–EC controlled by the ERM internal transport, providing better insight into the dynamic of the material. Other recommendations are referred to the improvement of the model and the uncertainty evaluation and are available in deliverable D4 of this project.

With the development of the numerical model describing the transport processes inside the used ERM and enabling the prediction of the compounds release into the test chamber air, the aims of Objective 4 have been achieved. A detailed guideline with recommendations on the customised design and dimensioning of the ERM has been published (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12749007>).

Impact

To maximise the impact of the project and ensure a wide dissemination of the knowledge generated, a website has been created and permanently updated. A Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) with 20 members was set up containing representatives from the EU-LCI working group, indoor emission testing laboratories, labelling schemes, manufacturers of construction products, regulators, and standardisation bodies. News was furthermore posted in the LinkedIn group "VOC measurements". In total, the consortium have published one paper and submitted two articles to high-ranking scientific journals, participated in 8 conferences and organised training for the stakeholder community in the form of a webinar and a workshop. Any activities undertaken within the project runtime are summarised below.

Impact on industrial and other user communities

The project engaged with industrial and end user communities through the set-up of its Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB). The SAB met twice (16 February 2022 and 08 December 2022) in ordinary meetings and a third time in the context of a webinar on 11 April 2024 entitled *Metrology for Indoor Air Quality – Reference materials for QA/QC of the emission test chamber procedure* which allowed a broader audience of 56–64 persons to learn about and discuss the project results. Apart from that, the project benefitted from the active support of the single SAB members that provided advice or sample material for test purposes.

The relevant industrial user communities were partly involved in the validation of the ERMs and gCRMs developed in this project in terms of training activities and an inter-laboratory comparison. On 18 October 2023, a stakeholder workshop entitled *Metrology for Indoor Air Quality* took place at the premises of project partner VITO in Mol, Belgium. In total, 14 participants attended the event in person. Besides information on the project

outcome, 3 participants took the opportunity to take VOC gas samples at VITO's dynamic preparation line with their own equipment for own QC purposes. The gas standard contained the compounds of the gCRMs. Data obtained from these measurements were furthermore used for the validation work. Shortly after the workshop, the first part of the inter-laboratory comparisons (gCRMs) on the reference products took place. Eight participants including stakeholders took part. Part 2 (ERMs) started later in January 2024. As well, 8 participants including stakeholders took part.

Impact on the metrology and scientific communities

An important finding from the project was that the reservoir materials required for stable ERMs must be optimised specifically for each VOC. The project demonstrated the feasibility of this and showed ways in which NMIs/DIs can adopt the methodology and extend their portfolio of reference materials. Further development by institutes outside the MetrIAQ consortium is important, as the original plans to commercialise the ERM have been thwarted by a change in BAM's thematic focus. Nonetheless, BAM plans to use the ERMs to organise an international RRT for the emission test chamber method according to EN 16516 and ISO 16000-9 on next possible occasion. Further to this, VSL intends to develop new calibration services on the project's development of dynamic and static reference materials.

The partners in this consortium are actively involved in the CCQM Gas Analysis Working Group (GAWG) and in EURAMET Metrology in Chemistry Technical Committee (TC-MC) and the outputs from this project were presented to them. The successful development of gPRMs and gCRMs will support the organisation of future Key Comparisons organised by the CCQM-GAWG and EURAMET TC-MC and will allow new calibration and measurement capability claims in the field of indoor air and VOC analysis. The gained know-how can be used by the scientific community and by other reference material providers for the preparation of similar calibration standards.

One paper on research results achieved during the project was already published and two further papers have been submitted for publication in high impact peer-reviewed scientific journals. As mentioned above, a workshop and an online webinar on the preparation of traceable and accurate gCRMs and ERMs was held, to which representatives of industry (both manufacturers and users), academic, standardisation and users were invited. POLITO have implemented project findings in educational courses at bachelor and master levels in architecture and mining engineering to promote young academics.

Project results were presented at 8 national and international conferences, e.g., the 36th European Colloid & Interface Society Conference (4-9 September 2022, Crete, Greece), the 10th International Symposium on modern principles of air monitoring and biomonitoring (Airmon) (7-10 November 2022, Bristol, United Kingdom), 21st International Metrology Congress (CIM) (7-10 March 2023, Lyon, France), the 18th Healthy Buildings 2023 Europe Conference (11-14 June 2023, Aachen, Germany), and the GAS Analysis 2024 (30 January – 1 February 2024, Paris, France).

Impact on relevant standards

The project aimed to provide impact for all standards describing procedures for the determination of chemical emissions from materials for interior use and requiring the use of emission test chambers, such as EN 16516, EN 16402, EN 16738, ISO 16000 series, ISO 12219 series. They all have similar QA/QC requirements in common and recommend the use of external references. With the validation data acquired in this project the total uncertainty of measurement results obtained with the test chamber method was determined and published in form of reporting documents to the respective standardisation committees for use in upcoming revision work.

The consortium faced the problem that the relevant committees either met very rarely or not at all during the project period. Every meeting that took place was used to report on project results or information was sent by email to the secretariat and the convenor of the committees if no meetings had taken place.

In June 2021, June and October 2022, the project informed CEN/TC 351/WG 2 on the project's progress at its regular meetings. In April and September 2022, as well as in September 2023 ISO/TC 146 SC 6/WG 3 was informed about the activities of the project. The feedback was very positive, particularly with regard to future exploitation routes after completion of the project. As meetings in other addressed committees, i.e., CEN/TC 421 and CEN/TC 437, did not take place, the respective chairpersons were actively contacted and informed in May 2023.

The project's outcome that might be relevant to the targeted standardisation committees is reported in detail in six deliverable reports, which were made available to them for their work.

Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts

The project aimed to support the longer-term market position of European manufacturers of low-emitting products through the availability of better reference materials and hence increased reliability of testing. For the first time, primary gas standards (gPRM) are available for the EN 16516 check standard, which can be used to certify secondary gas standards and would therefore be available to the global network of testing institutes. Together with the candidate ERMs developed in this project, strong reference products are available that promote improved comparability of emission test results. Although the best results with ERMs in terms of a stable emission profile have so far only been achieved with two porous materials for *n*-hexadecane and μ -capsules filled with D-limonene, the way has been paved for further development by, e.g., other research institutes.

Once, the declaration of emission data for CE marking is mandatory, more reliable testing will also increase consumer confidence in the product and the manufacturer, and thus increase sales. A similar effect on voluntary evaluation schemes that help consumers make decisions when choosing low-emitting products is also expected. Moreover, an improved comparability in emissions tests strengthens customers' trust in these labels, promotes fair competition between manufacturers, and safeguards the European common market in future building products.

The improvement of the metrological infrastructure in the field of materials emissions testing supports the long-term European harmonisation of the health-based evaluation of indoor emissions from construction products regulated by the CPR. This will support a higher level of consumer protection and should improve the health and well-being of the citizens. Furthermore, the results of this project might give additional impetus to those European member states that still are in the early stages of implementing an infrastructure for emissions testing, such as Slovenia.

- Press release “BAM develops reference material for better indoor air”, published on 4 November 2021
- Publication in professional press: “Bessere Luft in Innenräumen” (in German), published in ReinRaumTechnik, Vol. 24, January 2022

List of publications

de Krom, I. et al (2022) 'Metrological generation of SI-traceable gas-phase standards and reference materials for (semi-) volatile organic compounds', *Measurement Science and Technology*, 34 p. 35018. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/aca704>

This list is also available here: <https://www.euramet.org/repository/research-publications-repository-link/>

Project start date and duration:		01 June 2021, 36 months
Coordinator: Dr Matthias Richter, BAM		Tel: +49 30 8104 4132
Project website address: https://metriAQ.eu		E-mail: matthias.richter@bam.de
Chief Stakeholder Organisation: GEV – Association for the Control of Emissions in Products for Flooring Installation, Adhesives and Building Materials		Chief Stakeholder Contact: Klaus Winkels klaus.winkels@emicode.com
Internal Funded Partners:	External Funded Partners:	Unfunded Partners:
1. BAM, Germany	4. Eurofins, Denmark	-
2. TUBITAK, Turkey	5. FhG, Germany	
3. VSL, Netherlands	6. POLITO, Italy	
	7. VITO, Belgium	
	8. ZAG, Slovenia	